

Learning Designers: To define or not to define

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While the profession of ‘Learning Designer’ has many pseudonyms and various emergent and liminal qualities, it is not as new as many might like to contend. Learning Design is a heterogeneous profession that famously takes in often multi-skilled communicators, teachers, artists, technicians, psychologists, therapists and taxidermists. Previous studies have explored competency standards to better clarify and professionalise the role ([Hinze, M., Altena, S. & Ng, R. 2022](#)). With various degrees, qualifications and standards being put forward from both institutions, unions and professional bodies intersecting with increasingly corporatised and systematised university cultures seeking to hold the third space to account, it is timely to ask: Should Learning Designers be defined?

This Third Space Slowposium activity pulled apart the pros and cons of this thorny question and sought to have Learning Designers themselves input their opinions into the topic in a structured way using a Kialo board to facilitate a democratic voice from all participants. Participants added pro and con claims below each other’s points, creating an interactive discussion map. Kialo was a useful way of visually structuring debate and allowing participants to see how ideas were connected, supported, or challenged.

We structured the debate in Kialo to canvass the topic of establishing professional competency standards for Learning Design and probe the tensions between professionalisation and flexibility. We saw strong support for standards to establish credibility, career pathways, and quality assurance alongside significant concerns about potentially limiting diversity, innovation, and accessibility within the field. The interdisciplinary nature of learning design work requires flexible, inclusive standards that acknowledge overlapping competencies.

There is a need for further research, discussion and exploration of competency standards in the public domain. From our reflections on the session, we would suggest several middle-ground approaches and critical success factors. These include the need for multiple levels creating different standards for different contexts, building in systematic review and updating processes from the start, and evaluating competency based on evidence from experience and portfolios rather than only formal credentials.

The debate reveals a maturing profession grappling with fundamental questions about identity, quality, and inclusivity. The strongest approach would likely combine the legitimate benefits of professional standards with safeguards against their potential negative consequences.

Reference

Hinze, M., Altena, S. & Ng, R. (2022, December 4–7). Reconnecting with ourselves? Developing standards and competencies for Learning Designers [Panel]. *39th International Conference on Innovation, Practice and Research in the Use of Educational Technologies in Tertiary Education, ASCILITE 2022, Sydney, NSW, Australia*.
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